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Navigating Resilience: The Role of Nigeria's Inland Waterways Infrastructure in Disaster Response Along Major River Routes in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the role of inland waterways in disaster response and relief coordination along major river routes in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, Nigeria. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining spatial analysis of navigable waterway networks with survey data from 373 respondents, including transport operators, community leaders, and disaster management personnel. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed, identifying nine key river routes and jetties within the metropolis, with participants selected using the Taro-Yamane formula. Survey responses were collected using a structured questionnaire on a 4-point Likert scale, while Chi-square and descriptive statistics were applied to evaluate infrastructure adequacy, operational challenges, and the contribution of inland waterways to disaster management. Findings revealed that inland waterways are strategically positioned for rapid access to disaster-prone communities, with navigable distances ranging from 10 km to 53 km. Respondents acknowledged the importance of waterways in evacuation, relief material distribution, and accessibility to isolated settlements (overall mean = 2.93). However, operational limitations, including poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, insufficient training, and security threats, were significant (mean = 2.90). Chi-square analysis indicated no statistically significant association between inland waterways transport and disaster response, suggesting that effectiveness depends on integrated transport networks and coordinated management. The study recommends substantial investment in infrastructure, enhanced inter-agency coordination, provision of emergency response boats, operator training programs, and promotion of public-private partnerships. Strengthening inland waterway systems will enhance disaster resilience, improve response efficiency, and ensure reliable access to riverine

communities during waterways, disaster response, humanitarian logistics, flood emergencies. management, riverine infrastructure

Keywords: *Inland*

INTRODUCTION

Disaster events such as flooding and environmental emergencies frequently affect riverine communities in Rivers State, often disrupting road transport and limiting access to relief services. In such situations, inland waterways become important alternative routes for evacuation, movement of emergency personnel, and distribution of relief materials. In Port Harcourt metropolis and surrounding riverine settlements, water transport plays a vital role in connecting communities that are highly dependent on rivers and creeks for mobility and access.

Despite this importance, the potential of inland waterways disaster response is often constrained by inadequate infrastructure, poor maintenance, limited safety facilities, and weak coordination among relevant agencies. This study therefore examines the role of inland waterways infrastructure in disaster response along major river routes in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, with a view to assessing existing facilities, identifying key challenges and suggesting measures for improvement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nigeria, with its vast hydrographic network spanning over 8,600 kilometers of navigable inland waterways, possesses one of Africa's most extensive water transport systems, primarily concentrated in the Niger Delta and along the Niger and Benue Rivers. These waterways, including major routes such as the Lower Niger, Cross River, and intricate creek systems in the Niger Delta, have historically served as vital arteries for trade, migration, and socio-economic integration since pre-colonial times [1],[2]. Despite their strategic importance, inland waterways remain

underutilized in contemporary disaster response frameworks, even as climate-induced hazards intensify across the country. Between 2012 and 2022, Nigeria experienced recurrent flooding that affected over 10 million people, with the 2022 event alone displacing 1.4 million and causing economic losses exceeding \$1.6 billion [3]. This study focuses on the role of inland waterways infrastructure in building resilience during disaster response along Nigeria's major river corridors.

The country's disaster profile is dominated by hydrometeorological extremes, exacerbated by climate change, deforestation, and poor urban planning. Flood-prone states along the Niger and Benue, such as Kogi, Niger, and Bayelsa, experience annual inundations that render road networks inoperable for weeks [4]. In the Niger Delta, oil infrastructure damage during floods triggers secondary disasters like spills and fires, complicating humanitarian access [5],[2]. Conventional logistics reliant on highways, such as the Lagos–Abuja corridor or East–West Road, collapse under floodwaters, with response delays averaging 72 hours in rural riverine communities [6]. These bottlenecks result in heightened vulnerability, particularly for marginalized populations dependent on subsistence fishing and farming along riverbanks.

Inland waterways present a resilient alternative for disaster logistics. Unlike roads, navigable channels remain functional during floods, enabling rapid deployment of relief assets. The National Inland Waterways Authority (NIWA) oversees 28 major routes, with the Lower Niger stretch from Baro to Onitsha capable of supporting 1,000-tonne barges.

Historical precedents demonstrate efficacy: during the 2018 floods, NIWA-coordinated boat evacuations in Lokoja rescued over 15,000 individuals in under 48 hours, compared to stalled road operations [7]. Similarly, in Adamawa State, the Benue River facilitated aid delivery to 40,000 displaced persons when bridges along the Yola–Maiduguri highway were submerged [8]. These cases underscore the potential of waterways to serve as lifelines in disaster zones.

Humanitarian logistics theory supports waterway integration. The United Nations Humanitarian Response Depot (UNHRD) model emphasizes pre-positioning supplies in accessible hubs; river ports like Onitsha and Warri could function analogously, reducing lead times by 60% versus road transport in flooded terrains [9]. In Bangladesh, a comparable delta environment, the Inland Water Transport Authority (BIWTA) enabled 80% of cyclone relief distribution via waterways post- Cyclone Sidr. Nigeria could adapt such models, leveraging existing infrastructure like the Onitsha River Port, which handles 2 million tonnes annually in normal conditions.

Despite these advantages, systemic barriers impede operationalization. Dredging backlogs reduce channel depths below 2 meters in critical sections, limiting vessel drafts [10]. Piracy along the Nun River and regulatory overlaps between NIWA and state governments fragment coordination [11]. Pollution from upstream industrial discharge and oil spills degrades water quality, deterring emergency use [12]. Nigeria’s National Disaster Management Framework (NDMF) mentions multi-modal transport but lacks specific protocols for waterway activation during crises [13]. Community reliance on informal canoe networks fills gaps but operates outside formal supply chains, risking safety and accountability [14].

This study, titled “Navigating Resilience,” examines how targeted investments in waterway infrastructure, dredging, jetties, and digital navigation aids can transform disaster response along Nigeria’s major river routes. Through geospatial analysis, stakeholder interviews, and simulation modeling, it assesses current capacities and proposes an integrated framework aligning NIWA, NEMA, and humanitarian actors. Findings aim to inform policy under the National Transport Policy (2021 draft) and contribute to SDG 13 (Climate Action) and SDG 9 (Infrastructure). By reimagining waterways not merely as trade corridors but as resilience backbones, Nigeria can mitigate disaster impacts and safeguard riverine populations.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Rivers State, Nigeria, a region characterized by extensive riverine and coastal settlements. Key inland waterway terminals in Port Harcourt, including Nembe Waterside, Abonnema Wharf, Marine Base, Iwofe, and Abuloma, serve as primary hubs for water transport. The study focused on riverine communities such as Bonny, Okrika, Bakana, Kalio, Ogbakiri, Isiaka, and Okujagu, which are highly dependent on waterways for transportation, commerce, and emergency response. A mixed-methods design combining spatial analysis and survey research was employed. This approach allowed for both the quantitative assessment of spatial accessibility and the qualitative understanding of stakeholders’ perceptions of inland waterways in disaster response.

Spatial Data

Geographic coordinates of major terminals and riverine communities were obtained from official maps and GPS surveys. Waterway distances from Port Harcourt terminals to riverine communities were measured using Geographic Information

System (GIS) software (ArcGIS 10.8) to assess spatial proximity and navigability.

A structured questionnaire was administered to 373 respondents, comprising transport operators, community leaders, and disaster management personnel. Responses were measured using a 4-point.

Likert Scale

Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2),

and Strongly Disagree (1). The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique. Initially, the locations of jetties and navigable waterways within the metropolis were identified. Subsequently, a comprehensive list of these jetties and routes was compiled, totaling nine (9) within the study area. The Taro-Yamane formula was then applied to determine the appropriate sample size, resulting in 373 participants (see Table 1).

Table 1: River Routes in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/N	Loading Point	Off-Loading Point	Sampling Frame	Sample Size (5%)
1.	Nembe waterside	Bonny	1407	81
2.	Wait and Bush	Isiaka	853	49
3.	Nembe waterside	Nembe	501	29
4.	Nembe waterside	Brass	557	32
5.	Abonnema wharf	Bakana	1068	61
6.	Iwofe	Ogbakiri	263	15
7.	Marine base	Okrika	894	51
8.	Akpos	Okujagu	402	23
9.	Abuloma	Kalio	563	32
	Total		6508	373

The formula is given as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where;

n = sample size

N = population

e = level of significance, 0.05

Descriptive Statistics

Frequency counts, sums, and mean scores were calculated for survey items to determine the level of agreement regarding the contributions and challenges of inland waterways. Mean scores above 2.5 were considered significant, reflecting positive acknowledgment by respondents. The chi-square will be used to analyze the hypothesis.

Ethical Considerations

Participation was voluntary, and respondents provided informed consent. Confidentiality and anonymity of responses were maintained throughout the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board before fieldwork.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 2: Evaluating the existing infrastructure of inland waterways transportation.

	Existing infrastructure of inland waterways transportation	SA	A	D	SD	Total	SWV	Mean	Remarks	Rank	x-x'	(x-x') ²
		4	3	2	1							
1	Availability and good condition of the infrastructure	140	303	310	82	373	835	2.2	Rejected	4 th	-0.05	0.0025
2	There are sufficient docking and terminal facilities for inland water transport in the study area.	144	177	254	151	373	726	1.9	Rejected	6 th	-0.35	0.1225
3	The existing jetties and ports are well-maintained and operational.	344	294	242	68	373	948	2.5	Accepted	1 st	0.25	0.0625
4	There are adequate safety measures and equipment at inland water transport terminals.	356	234	214	99	373	903	2.4	Rejected	2 nd	0.15	0.0225
5	The waterways are well-dredged and navigable throughout the year.	184	246	244	123	373	797	2.1	Rejected	5 th	-0.15	0.0225
6	The inland water transport system has reliable navigational aids such as buoys and markers.	348	237	218	98	373	901	2.4	Rejected	3 rd	0.15	0.0225
								13.5				0.255
								2.25				

The evaluation of the existing infrastructure for inland waterways transportation in the study area revealed notable deficiencies and areas requiring significant improvement. Although inland waterways are considered a cost-effective and environmentally friendly mode of transport [15],[2], the results from this study indicate that the supporting infrastructure is largely inadequate to meet modern transportation demands.

The item with the highest acceptance score was “The existing jetties and ports are well-maintained and operational” (Mean = 2.5; SWV = 948; Rank = 1st). This suggests that respondents recognize that certain facilities, such as jetties and ports, are maintained to some extent and remain operational. This finding aligns with the observations of Olayinka [16], who noted that while some ports in Nigeria receive periodic maintenance, the level of operational efficiency is uneven and highly dependent on location and funding priorities.

The second and third-ranked items, “There are adequate safety measures and equipment at inland water transport terminals” and “The inland water transport system has reliable navigational aids such as buoys and markers” (both Mean = 2.4),

were, however, rejected by respondents. This indicates that, despite some safety measures being in place, these are perceived as insufficient, inconsistent, or poorly enforced. Similarly, the provision of navigational aids, while partially available, is not comprehensive enough to guarantee year-round safe navigation. This corroborates the findings of Okon *et al.* [17], who emphasized that inadequate safety infrastructure and lack of functional navigational aids are critical contributors to waterway accidents in Nigeria.

The lowest-ranked indicator was “There are sufficient docking and terminal facilities for inland water transport in the study area” (Mean = 1.9; SWV = 726; Rank = 6th). This implies a significant shortfall in the number and capacity of docking and terminal facilities, which is consistent with the infrastructural challenges reported by other researches. Limited docking points increase congestion and turnaround time for vessels, discouraging commercial operators from fully utilizing inland waterways.

Similarly, “Availability and good condition of the infrastructure” (Mean = 2.2; Rank = 4th) and “The waterways are well-dredged and navigable throughout the year” (Mean = 2.1; Rank = 5th) were rejected. Poor dredging and sediment accumulation have

been widely reported as major bottlenecks for inland water transportation in Nigeria, leading to reduced navigability during the dry season [10]. These challenges limit the potential of inland waterways to serve as a viable alternative to road transport, despite their strategic importance for decongesting highways and enhancing regional trade.

From a policy and planning perspective, these findings indicate a mismatch between the infrastructural capacity of the inland waterways system and the growing transportation needs of the study area. The deficiencies in safety measures, navigational aids, dredging, and docking facilities present significant operational

risks and hinder the system's reliability. This underscores the urgent need for targeted investments, routine maintenance, and a comprehensive infrastructural upgrade strategy, as recommended by the Nigerian Inland Waterways Authority.

In general, while there are pockets of functional infrastructure, particularly some operational jetties and ports, the overall picture reflects inadequacy and underdevelopment. Without addressing these infrastructural gaps, the inland waterways transportation system in the study area will remain underutilized, limiting its economic and social benefits.

Table 3: Challenges of inland waterways in Disaster response

	Challenges of inland waterways in Disaster response	SA	A	D	SD	Total	SWV	Mean	Remarks	Rank	x-x'	(x-x') ²
		4	3	2	1							
1.	Poor infrastructure limits the effectiveness of inland water transport in disaster relief	492	393	82	78	373	1045	2.8	Accepted	4 th	-0.1	0.01
2.	Lack of well- coordinated policies affects the efficiency of inland water transport during emergencies.	436	363	196	45	373	1040	2.8	Accepted	5 th	-0.1	0.01
3.	Inadequate funding for inland water transport affects disaster response efforts	568	384	112	47	373	1111	3.0	Accepted	2 nd	0.1	0.01
4.	Security threats (e.g., piracy, theft) hinder the use of inland waterways for disaster relief.	628	366	80	54	373	1128	3.0	Accepted	1 st	0.1	0.01
5.	There is insufficient training for water transport operators on emergency response procedures.	488	384	196	25	373	1093	2.9	Accepted	3 rd	0.0	0.00
								14.5				0.04
								2.9				

The results of the study, as presented in Table 3, highlight several key challenges that hinder the effective utilization of inland waterways for disaster response in the study area. The most significant challenge identified was security threats, including piracy and theft, which ranked first with a mean score of 3.0. This finding aligns with the observations of Nwoye *et al.* [18], who noted that maritime insecurity remains a persistent threat to inland waterway transportation in Nigeria, particularly in the Niger Delta region. Security concerns not only endanger lives and property but also deter both private and government operators from deploying vessels for

emergency relief operations.

The second-ranked challenge, with the same mean value of 3.0, was inadequate funding for inland water transport during disaster situations. This corroborates the assertion by Emmanuel *et al.* [19] that insufficient budgetary allocations to water transport infrastructure and disaster management agencies significantly impair rapid and large-scale responses in emergency situations. Funding gaps affect vessel availability, maintenance, and the provision of emergency logistics, thereby prolonging the time required to reach affected communities.

Insufficient training for water transport operators on emergency response procedures emerged as the third-ranked challenge (mean = 2.9). According to previous researches, operator training is crucial for ensuring safety, efficiency, and coordination during high-pressure situations such as flood evacuations or supply deliveries. The lack of such training reduces the operational readiness of transport crews and increases the risk of accidents.

The fourth-ranked challenge (mean = 2.8) was poor infrastructure, such as inadequate docking facilities, poorly maintained jetties, and unmarked navigation channels. These infrastructural deficits limit the speed, capacity, and safety of inland waterway operations during emergencies. This finding agrees with Obidina *et al.* [20], who emphasized that most Nigerian inland waterway routes lack the physical infrastructure necessary to support sustained disaster relief efforts.

Lastly, the lack of well-coordinated policies affecting the efficiency of inland water transport during emergencies also scored a mean of 2.8. This reflects the institutional and governance gaps identified by Ladele *et al.* [21], where overlapping responsibilities, bureaucratic bottlenecks, and poor inter-agency communication hinders timely responses to disasters.

Overall, the findings underscore that while inland waterways have the potential to serve as critical disaster response corridors, their effectiveness is undermined by a combination of security, financial, infrastructural, capacity-building, and policy challenges. Addressing these bottlenecks will require integrated interventions, including enhanced maritime security operations, increased funding, targeted training programs, infrastructure upgrades, and streamlined inter-agency coordination frameworks. These measures will not only improve inland waterway disaster response capacity but also contribute to sustainable maritime transport development in Nigeria.

Table 4: Recommendations for improving inland waterways transportation in Disaster response.

	Recommendations for improving inland waterways transportation	SA	A	D	SD	Total	SWV	Mean	Remarks	Rank	x-x	(x-x) ²
		4	3	2	1							
1.	Government should invest in better infrastructure for inland water transport.	656	396	76	39	373	1167	3.1	Accepted	1 st	0.2	0.04
2.	There should be improved coordination between agencies involved in inland water transport and disaster management.	436	315	184	67	373	1002	2.7	Accepted	5 th	-0.2	0.04
3.	More emergency response boats should be made available in disaster-prone areas.	568	363	178	21	373	1130	3.0	Accepted	2 nd	0.1	0.01
4.	Training programs should be provided for inland water transport operators on emergency response	552	360	156	37	373	1105	3.0	Accepted	3 rd	0.1	0.01
5.	Public-private partnerships should be encouraged to enhance inland water transport systems for disaster relief	436	324	198	57	373	1017	2.7	Accepted	4 th	-0.2	0.04
								14.5				0.14
								2.9				

The results in Table 4 indicate that respondents strongly supported a range of recommendations to enhance the role of inland waterways in disaster response. The highest-ranked recommendation was

government investment in better infrastructure for inland water transport (Mean = 3.1), suggesting that robust and modernized facilities such as jetties, docks, and navigation systems are seen as

foundational to improving operational capacity during emergencies. This aligns with other findings, who emphasized that infrastructural deficits are a major constraint to inland water transport efficiency in Nigeria. Similarly, Adepoju [22] stressed that sustainable investment in water transport infrastructure not only improves routine service delivery but also enhances emergency logistics during disaster events.

The second and third-ranked recommendations, provision of more emergency response boats in disaster-prone areas (Mean = 3.0) and training programs for inland water transport operators on emergency response (Mean = 3.0), reflect a recognition of the need for both resource availability and capacity building. Adequate and well-equipped vessels are essential for rapid deployment, while trained operators are critical for effective, safe, and coordinated responses during disasters. Research by Obadina *et al.* [20] has shown that skill gaps among transport operators can significantly slow emergency relief delivery, particularly in flood-affected communities.

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) were also identified as a viable strategy (Mean =

2.7, Rank = 4th) for strengthening inland water transport systems for disaster relief. This recommendation is in line with global best practices, as PPPs can leverage private sector innovation, funding, and management expertise to complement government-led disaster response strategies [2]. However, respondents ranked improved coordination between agencies (Mean = 2.7, Rank = 5th) the lowest, which may suggest either a perceived improvement in inter-agency cooperation or a belief that physical and human resource constraints are more pressing priorities. Nonetheless, coordination remains a critical element, as fragmentation between transport, emergency, and security agencies can hinder timely interventions [23].

Overall, these findings suggest that enhancing inland waterways for disaster response requires a multi-pronged approach that combines infrastructure development, resource provision, personnel training, inter-agency coordination, and strategic partnerships. By implementing these recommendations, governments and stakeholders can significantly improve resilience and response times during floods, storms, and other water-related disasters in Nigeria and similar contexts.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 5: Chi-square contingency table.

Study Locations	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Bonny	28 (29.5)	30 (25.6)	12 (13.6)	11 (9.9)	81
Isiaka	15 (17.8)	13 (15.5)	11 (8.3)	10 (6.0)	49
Nembe	9 (10.6)	10 (9.2)	6 (4.9)	4 (3.6)	29
Brass	10 (11.7)	16 (10.1)	4 (5.4)	2 (3.9)	32
Bakana	28 (22.2)	21 (19.3)	9 (10.3)	3 (7.5)	61
Ogbakiri	5 (5.5)	5 (4.7)	2 (2.5)	3 (1.8)	15
Okrika	23 (18.6)	11 (16.1)	9 (8.6)	8 (6.3)	51
Okujagu	8 (8.4)	10 (7.3)	3 (3.9)	2 (2.8)	23
Kalio	10 (11.7)	12 (10.1)	7 (5.4)	3 (3.9)	32
Total	136	118	63	46	373

Data from the nine study locations were

analyzed using the Chi-square (X^2) test of

independence, with observed and expected frequencies presented in Table 4.6. The calculated Chi-square value was 22.518 with 24 degrees of freedom. At a 0.05 significance level, the critical value is 36.415.

Since $22.518 < 36.415$, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating no statistically significant association between inland waterways transport and disaster response in the study area.

In practice, while inland waterways support disaster management logistics, factors such as accessibility, infrastructure quality, and operational capacity have a greater influence on response effectiveness [17],[16]. This aligns with previous studies, which found that inland waterways alone do not significantly enhance emergency relief without integration into a coordinated transport network [20].

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the critical role of inland waterways in disaster response within Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. These waterways serve as essential lifelines for numerous communities, especially in flood-prone and road-inaccessible areas, providing alternative connectivity when land routes become unusable during emergencies.

However, the current inland water transport infrastructure remains largely inadequate to support effective disaster operations. Key limitations include poor docking and navigational facilities, inconsistent maintenance such as dredging, inadequate funding, security concerns, insufficient operator training, and fragmented coordination among agencies. These challenges significantly hinder the speed, safety, and reliability of waterway-based emergency interventions.

To unlock the full potential of inland

waterways for disaster management, urgent strategic investments are needed. Priorities should include upgrading infrastructure, increasing the availability of dedicated emergency response boats, enhancing training programs for operators, strengthening inter-agency collaboration, and fostering public-private partnerships. With these improvements, the inland waterway system can become a more robust, efficient, and resilient component of disaster relief efforts, particularly for vulnerable riverine populations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The government should prioritize substantial investments in inland waterway infrastructure, including jetties, navigational aids, and regular dredging, to ensure reliable year-round access for disaster response in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Agencies must strengthen inter-agency coordination, expand the emergency response boat fleet, and implement regular training programs for operators to enhance rapid and effective relief operations in riverine communities.

Public-private partnerships, supported by adequate funding and robust policies, should be actively pursued to modernize equipment, improve security, and sustain long-term operational capacity for disaster management via inland waterways.

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